

RECENT REFORMS IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6694078>

Annotation: Since the first years of independence in our country, the development of the educational system has been increasing to the level of public policy, our children have acquired modern knowledge and professions in conditions suitable to the world standards, ensuring the maturation of physically and spiritually mature people, realization of their abilities and talents, intellectual potential, perfection of loyalty and dedication to the In the last 5 years, the oily education system has also been making positive changes in the system as a result of many innovations and reforms. In this article, the reforms and innovations in the higher education system are analyzed and considered.

Keywords: higher education system, reforms, News, Problem, Solution, Innovation, Technology in education, credit module system.

Nowadays, all spheres of life in New Uzbekistan have become an arena of deep reforms. It is impossible not to wave about the changes in the educational system, which are considered the basis of the social sphere in this process. In recent years, practical work on the organization of all stages of the educational system on the basis of modern requirements has entered a decisive stage in our country. The main part of the reforms carried out in the field of education, of course, is the reforms in the higher education system.

The conference on the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, approved by the decree of the head of our state on October 8, 2019, with the aim of establishing the priority directions of systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training of highly qualified personnel who think independently, modernizing higher education, This document was based on such tasks as accelerating development, training of competitive personnel, effective organization of scientific and innovative activities and development of integration of Science, Education and production in order to strengthen international cooperation.

The content of the conference reflects the priorities of the reform of the higher education system of our country. It includes the expansion of the level of coverage in higher educational institutions, the improvement of the quality of education, the introduction of digital technologies and educational platforms, the involvement of young people in scientific activities, the formation of innovative structures, the commercialization of the results of scientific research,

the achievement of international prestige and many other specific directions. All this serves to raise the educational process to a new level of quality.

It is no secret to anyone that today the world-famous institutions of higher education are considered major centers of science. Now new universities, branches of leading universities of the world are being established. For example, in the last 5 years, 47 new higher education institutions, including branches of foreign universities, have been established in our country and the number of higher educational institutions has reached 125. On the basis of the system of Public-Private Partnership, the activities of non-governmental higher education institutions are launched. Having studied the opinion of the population, correspondence and evening forms of Education have been restored, quotas for admission are being increased. The level of coverage of school graduates in higher education reached from 9 percent in 2016 to 25 percent in 2020. It was created to ensure the professional development and internship of professors and teachers in higher education and research institutions abroad. Their monthly salary increased by an average of 2,5 times compared to 2018 year. Since this year, 10 higher educational institutions have been transferred to the system of self-financing.

The fact that the number of state grants allocated to higher education was increased by at least 25 percent, the number of grants for girls of families in need of admission to higher education increased by 2 times and reached to 2 thousand further increased the scope of coverage for higher education. One of the most important innovations in the education system was the transfer of 65 academic lyceums to the disposal of higher educational institutions with the aim of increasing the unity between higher education institutions and the lower sections of the education system, as well as the attachment of 187 technical schools to the universities and Network Enterprises.

In the XXI century, which was called the age of Information Technology, the development of Science in all spheres of life – industry, construction, chemistry, agriculture, textile, mechanical engineering and other spheres, the creation of innovations in this regard became a vital necessity. This process is now recognized in all countries of the world that are on the path of development. Special attention is paid to this process in our republic.

In the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated February 7, 2017, a number of tasks are set for the development of the social sphere, in particular, the spheres of education and science. The document provides for strengthening the material and technical base of educational

institutions, construction, repair and capital repair of new educational institutions, as well as providing them with modern educational and laboratory equipment, computer equipment and educational and methodical manuals.

"The tasks of higher education systems in the strategy of new Uzbekistan:

- Along with bringing the level of coverage to higher education to 50 percent, the main focus will be on improving the quality of Education. Up to 2026, will be included in the prestigious international ratings;

- Nearly 100 thousand-seat student dormitories will be restored in the next five years to improve students' living conditions;

- In order to create a competitive environment in higher education, until 2026, the number of private households will reach at least 50 units.

- "Admission to the doctorate is carried out on the basis of state order and payment-grant from the account of funds of interested organizations," - stressed President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his pre-election program.

In recent years, acceptance quotas have grown several times. In addition, I can say that this is mainly due to the targeted program of measures aimed at achieving this figure by 50 percent over the coming years, to further increase the prestige of higher educational institutions, as well as to improve the quality of education, reforms are waiting for this system. In this process, measures are also being taken to increase the academic level of teachers, to increase the level of teaching staff, and to increase the level of teaching staff. In the system of higher education, in general, only 4 percent of English Language teachers who teach at all stages of Education have an international certificate, indicating that the work that needs to be done in this regard is significant.

In addition, up to 2030, 85 percent of all educational institutions in the Republic, including the 2020/2021 academic year, 33 oily educational institutions were transferred to the credit-module system. Credit-module system, this is the process of organizing education, the evaluation model based on the aggregate of module technologies of teaching and credit measurement is summarized. Taking it as a whole, boorish is a multifaceted and complex systemic process. The principle of credit-module is given importance to two main issues: ensuring the independent performance of students and improving the knowledge of students. The following are recognized as the main functions of the credit-module system:

- Organization of educational processes on the basis of modules;
- single science, course (credit)assessment;
- assessment of students' knowledge on the basis of rating score;
- to enable students to draw up their curricula in an individual way;

— serves to increase the share of Independent Education in the educational process.

In this is an example of teaching lessons not only on the basis of innovative educational technologies, but also on the basis of exceptional learning, a new attitude to education, due to the demand of the labor market, the acquisition of necessary and deep theoretical knowledge, the formation of practical skills.

In conclusion, various innovations and reforms in the educational system in recent years have contributed to the increase in the quality of education in this oily educational system. In particular, through the module credit system, it is possible to positively influence the student's professional development and his / her career. That is, it is aimed at forming in themselves the human capital, which can meet modern requirements when they find their place in the labor market. The increase in quality in education also contributes to the training of potential personnel. From that, we also support all reforms and innovations in family education, as well as with the initiative in the future, we also aim to make many innovations in our family and to increase the experience of our teachers in foreign universities.

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